

STANDARDS-BASED GRADING TOOLS

Alors que tous les enseignants suisses connaissent Lehreroffice et que de plus en plus d'entre eux se familiarisent avec ces fonctionnalités sur schulwebseite.com, il existe bon nombre d'outils similaires, axés sur l'évaluation standardisée. Cet article propose une brève description des plus communément utilisés.

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The following tools can be used to help foreign language teachers collect data on learner performance in sophisticated ways – encouraging standards-based grading and monitoring learner progress. With the following tools, language teachers can directly enter the CEFR descriptors and record multiple instances of learner performance PER DESCRIPTOR.

Jump Rope
<https://www.jumpro.pe>

JumpRope allow teachers to collect data on what learners have learned (not just what they have done). Each score and set of items on tests and performance assessments have to be linked to standards so that standards-based reports can be generated. By working with this system, from the start teachers must think of what they are teaching and ultimately assessing.

Active Grade
<http://activegrade.com/>

Active Grade gives the example of Mike (<http://activegrade.com/#features>):
"Take Mike ... Mike's second semester of Spanish class is going pretty well and he's

learned a lot of new vocabulary but his current grade is a C because he struggled with conjugating verbs on his midterm exam. Mike may understand that he needs to work on conjugating verbs, but even with a high score on the final exam he may not be able to raise his "C" to an "A." Or worse yet, his teacher may have moved on from simple verb conjugation to irregular verbs and Mike would have no opportunity to demonstrate his understanding of the initial concept. With the ActiveGrade approach, Mike's teacher would work with him to identify that it's the future tense causing Mike's difficulties, and after Mike clearly demonstrates an improvement in and understanding of this practice, the intelligent calculation done by ActiveGrade can reflect that achievement in Mike's final grade, despite Mike's initial struggle on the midterm. Mike's final grade becomes a reflection of the core skills and concepts he's learned in Spanish class, not simply an average of how he scored on the tests and assignments given."

Active Grade provides anyone interested with a very good overview of what standards-based grading is and a starter kit to help teachers set up a standards-based grading policy in their classroom.

➤ PIÙ ARTICOLI SU QUESTO TEMA:
WWW.BABYLONIA.CH >
ARCHIVIO TEMATICO > [SCHEDE 6 E 3](#)

Traditional Math Gradebook

STUDENT	Homework 1	Homework 2	Quiz 1	Homework 3	Final Grd
Antonio P.	70%	78%	70%	75%	C
Arlene B.	76%	83%	76%	81%	B-
Benjamin P.	97%	95%	93%	98%	A
Bertha R.	70%	79%	70%	79%	C+

SBG Math Gradebook (ActiveGrade)

STUDENT	Add Like Fractions	Find Slope of Line	Find Area of Triangles
Antonio P.	3.5	3	3
Arlene B.	3.75	2	4
Benjamin P.	4	3.2	4
Bertha R.	3	2	2

Pearson Power School

<http://www.powerschool.com/powerschool-sis/>

PowerSchool includes a powerful gradebook and teacher tools that provide all the features teachers need in one place, making it easy-to-use and learn. All classes, rosters, student demographic information, grading periods, standards, rubrics and grades scales are automatically loaded into the gradebook. All data flows back to the central database in real time, providing all stakeholders, including parents and students, with instant visibility to assignments, scores, grades, comments and progress toward each standard.

Ken O'Conner writes about how Power School can be used for standards based grading here: <http://www.oconnorgrading.com/PowerTeacher.php>

Powerful Teacher Tools and Resources

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- Fast, easy attendance recording
- Automatic grade/standard calculation
- Schedules and student rosters automatically loaded and updated
- Link assignments to content for parents and students
- Supports co-teaching
- Supports district, state and Common Core Standards
- Email parents/guardians and students
- Create intervention groups and project teams and create "what-if" grade calculations
- Track each student's progress toward standards

Pearson Power School

Fresh Grade

<https://www.freshgrade.com>

Fresh Grade is a free tool offering a gradebook for standards-based grading and space for individual learner digital portfolios. On the website and Facebook site, they offer interesting discussions not only about the product, but also about assessment.

